

Book Presentation

RIVER CULTURE: A GLOBAL STUDY EXAMINES THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MAN AND NATURE

It is obvious that humanity, and planet Earth, with all its living beings, are in a severe crisis regarding the equitable and sustainable distribution of natural resources, especially continental water. In nature, exponential processes rarely occur over long periods of time because they are usually rapidly buffered by feedback mechanisms. In the Anthropocene, however, processes such as population growth, dam construction, or per capita demand for water grow exponentially, while the numbers of free-flowing rivers, or biological species or forms of culture tied to water, trend exponentially downward.

The River Culture Concept is an approach to restore harmony between humans and nature in the places where humanity first developed and spread: river valleys. A book just published by UNESCO, *River Culture: Life as a Dance in the Rhythm of Waters*, presents how differently humans and non-human organisms have adapted to the rhythms of natural floods and droughts, what factors promote and threaten this biocultural diversity, what actions can be taken to recover this diversity, and under what socio-cultural circumstances such actions are successfully stimulated and implemented.

The book has been designed to serve as a toolbox of examples, showing how river-related problems can be overcome, and how engaged societal groups have succeeded in implementing sustainable solutions, all over the world. On more than 900 pages, socio-ecological portraits of 28 rivers from 4 continents (Africa: 6, Asia: 7, Americas: 6, Europe: 9) are presented, five reviews summarize sustainable concepts for riverscape management in the Anthropocene, two chapters deal with artist's perspectives for environmental communication and one with gender equality. To make this toolbox available to everyone, authors have engaged a widely comprehensive language, and the electronic versions of all the chapters are freely available (and can be further shared via Creative Commons) at the document repository of UNESCO publishing.

Wantzen KM. (Ed.) 2023. *River Culture: Life as a Dance in the Rhythm of Waters*. UNESCO Publishing, Paris, 901+XV pp, ISBN 978-92-3-100540-4.

The book can be freely downloaded as [single chapters](#) or the [whole book](#).

A short summary is given in: Wantzen KM. 2022. River Culture: socioecology of the rhythm of the waters. The Geographical Journal [DOI: 10.1111/geoj.12476](https://doi.org/10.1111/geoj.12476)

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About the editor: Professor Wantzen's expertise covers ecology, biodiversity and human nature-interactions, specifically in freshwater systems and their aquatic-terrestrial interaction zones. After his PhD work at the Max-Planck-Institute of Limnology, he coordinated a research project on the Pantanal wetland at the Federal University of Mato Grosso, Brazil, later, he built up a research group at University of Konstanz. Since 2010, he holds a chair in Restoration Ecology of Aquatic Ecosystems at the University of Tours, and he is member of the Sustainability Cluster (FERED/RISE) at the University of Strasbourg. In 2014, he was nominated "UNESCO Chair Fleuves et Patrimoine", building up a global network on sustainable hydrosystem management (renominated in 2018 and 2022).